

Performance of MRP, RPS, and ConWIP in Stochastic Multi-Stage Systems: An Item-Level Simheuristic Study

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ABSTRACT

This study conducted a comprehensive comparison of three production planning and control systems – MRP, RPS, and ConWIP – across 18 stochastic multi-item, multi-stage production environments. The evaluation incorporated varying production system structures (flow, job, hybrid shops), planned utilization levels, and customer-required lead-time tightness. A simheuristic combining Simulated Annealing, Simulation Budget Management, and Exponential Range Reduction was applied to tune planning parameters at the item and component level, significantly enlarging the search space compared to earlier, system-level studies. The simheuristic consistently outperformed the baseline, with gains most pronounced under high utilization and complex structures. ConWIP proved most robust in medium- to high-load environments by stabilizing work-in-process. In contrast, MRP performed best under low utilization and relaxed due-dates, as demand-driven logic is most effective when congestion is minimal. While RPS was the least flexible and benefited least from tuning, it offered the highest efficiency with minimal computational overhead, providing a clear trade-off between optimization depth and responsiveness.

1 INTRODUCTION

Production planning aims to align system output with customer demand, serving as a key interface between operations and the market. Despite its central role, comprehensive evaluations of production planning and control systems (PPCS) remain scarce. This study extends current knowledge on PPCS performance in complex and uncertain environments. While prior simulation studies such as Thüerer et al. (2022) analyzed approaches like Kanban, MRP, OPT/DBR, and DDMRP under bottleneck conditions, broader assessments of stochastic, multi-stage systems with high variability are still missing.

Closing existing gaps in comparative PPCS research requires considering the dynamic and uncertain environments in which these systems operate. Such uncertainty stems from stochastic factors like fluctuating demand, process variability, and forecast errors (Altendorfer et al. 2016). Moreover, production systems must handle complex information flows – covering demand data, Bills of Materials, and routing information (Reuter et al. 2017) – that directly influence performance measures such as WIP, inventory, and tardiness costs (Axsäter 2015). To manage complexity and improve performance, firms rely on various production planning and control systems (PPCS), notably Material Requirements Planning (MRP), Reorder Point Systems (RPS), and Constant Work-In-Progress (ConWIP). ConWIP is valued for its simplicity and adaptability Framinan et al. (2003), while MRP and RPS have long been recognized as alternative planning approaches (Bregman 1994; Braglia and Gabbrielli 2001). However, selecting and parameterizing an appropriate PPCS remains difficult, as system characteristics and minor parameter changes can strongly affect outcomes.

Despite extensive research, comparative analyses of PPCS remain relatively scarce. Gupta and Snyder (2009) identified only 20 studies comparing multiple systems, with few additional contributions since (Miclo et al. 2019; Thüerer et al. 2022). Jodlbauer and Huber (2008) compared MRP, Kanban, ConWIP, and DBR in a multi-item, multi-stage flow shop, showing that ConWIP performs best when optimally parameterized but lacks robustness, while MRP proved more stable under uncertainty. Miclo et al. (2019)

analyzed DDMRP, MRP, and Kanban under varying demand conditions and found DDMRP superior, with MRP consistently performing worst. Thüerer et al. (2022) extended the Jodlbauer and Huber model by introducing a single bottleneck and varying due-date tightness while excluding stochastic effects. Their results confirmed the advantages of DBR and DDMRP over MRP, emphasizing that tighter due dates favor systems capable of achieving shorter production lead times. While these studies advanced comparative insights into PPCS performance, most relied on simplified or deterministic settings and considered a limited range of environmental characteristics (Gupta and Snyder 2009; Thüerer et al. 2022). However, real-world manufacturing is defined by complex multi-stage dependencies and high variability, which often lead to significant congestion effects and performance gaps in traditional push-based or non-integrated systems like MRP and RPS (Stevenson et al. 2005; Hopp and Spearman 2011; Thüerer et al. 2011), whereas more robust card-based control systems such as ConWIP aim to stabilize these effects by limiting work-in-process (Thüerer et al. 2011).

In response to these challenges, our study extends existing modeling approaches by transitioning from a parameterization differentiated by item groups to an individual optimization for each specific end item and component (Gansterer et al. 2014). While this approach facilitates a more granular optimization in complex environments characterized by stochastic demand and process variability (Altendorfer et al. 2016), it significantly increases numerical complexity by substantially enlarging the underlying search space. By applying simheuristic item-level optimization, we overcome the structural insensitivity of conventional planning that often ignores item-specific lead times and BOM variations (Axsäter and Rosling 1994; Axsäter 2015)

This study conducts a large-scale investigation of MRP, RPS, and ConWIP across 18 stochastic, multi-item, and multi-stage environments. We evaluate three fundamental archetypes—flow, job, and hybrid shops—which reflect recurring industrial configurations in sectors such as automotive, aerospace, electronics, and machinery. While not calibrated to a single plant, these structures ensure the broad relevance of our comparative analysis. Preliminary results were reported in Seiringer et al. (2024); however, that work neglected item-level parameters, due date tightness, simheuristic application, and budget management. Here, those results serve as the basis for designing the parameter ranges for the preliminary enumeration.

The scientific contribution of this study is structured around five key methodological pillars designed to address the gaps identified in current PPCS literature:

- (1) **Stochastic Complexity:** We introduce due-date tightness (Thüerer et al. 2022) as a third dimension to reflect varying levels of industrial lead-time pressure. Using discrete-event simulation, we analyze 18 unique environments. Crossing shop-load levels with the defined production archetypes captures the high-degree variability and stochastic dynamics — such as congestion effects and wait-time dependencies — inherent in multi-stage manufacturing (Altendorfer 2019; Pinedo 2022).
- (2) **Simheuristic Search Framework:** We utilize a framework combining Simulated Annealing (SA) and an adaptive simulation budget allocation to navigate the expanded, high-dimensional solution space and identify robust item-level configurations (Juan et al. 2015).
- (3) **Fair Comparison Related to Simulation Effort:** To ensure an unbiased comparison, predefined simulation budgets are applied uniformly across all PPCS. This ensures that performance gains are attributable to the control logic rather than disparate computational intensity.
- (4) **Granular Parameterization:** Most significantly, we transition to item-specific optimization, moving from group-based differentiation to individual parameterization for every part. This allows the PPCS to adapt to specific BOM characteristics, addressing the structural limitations of traditional, aggregated planning.

Our framework executes 162 experiments (18 environments \times 3 budget levels) comparing MRP, RPS, and ConWIP to address the following research questions:

- RQ1: How do PPCS best fit different production system structures, and how does item-level parameter decoupling reveal the structural performance limits of PPCS under varying shop loads and due date tightness?
- RQ2: What is the performance benefit of higher simulation budgets when applying simulation-based optimization using a simheuristics for PPCS (MRP, RPS, ConWIP)?
- RQ3: How does a predefined simulation budget influence PPCS performance (MRP, RPS, ConWIP) when using simheuristics for parameter tuning?

This research offers valuable insights for both academia and managerial practice. Academically, it addresses the research gap in PPCS comparisons across diverse environments while ensuring fairness through identical simulation budgets for parameter optimization. For managers, it analyzes the most effective PPCS under specific conditions and evaluates performance using simheuristics under limited simulation budgets.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 outlines the PPCS characteristics and simulation-based optimization methods. Section 3 describes the simulation model and shop structures. Section 4 presents the pre-simulation study, followed by the simheuristic results in Section 5. Section 6 concludes with final remarks and future research directions.

2 PRODUCTION PLANNING AND CONTROL SYSTEMS

To overview the three PPCSs, we first introduce four distinguishing characteristics. These are used to examine planning mechanisms, release logic, and associated parameters. Finally, we present and discuss simulation-based parameter optimization.

2.1 Characteristics

Firstly, PPCS can be classified based on their *operational mechanism* as either *push* or *pull*. The literature offers numerous definitions for these mechanisms, effectively summarized by Bertolini et al. (2015). We align upon the definition provided in Hopp and Spearman (2004), where a pull systems restrict the amount of WIP within the production system, in contrast to push systems, which do not impose an explicit limit on WIP. Secondly, PPCS are differentiated by their *demand orientation*, distinguishing between *demand-driven* systems and those that *authorize production*. *Demand-driven* systems use information on future demands to plan production, while systems that *authorize production* rely on downstream demand or customer withdrawal (Cochran and Kaylani 2008). Thirdly, PPCS can be categorized by their control structure, which is either *centralized* or *decentralized*. *Centralized* systems rely on a single authorization unit for production planning and order, whereas *decentralized* systems distribute decision-making to individual units on the shop floor level (Woschank et al. 2021). Fourth, *planning complexity* is assessed based on the number of planning parameters, distinguishing between *item-level* and *system-level* parameterization. *Item-level* parameterization requires setting specific parameters for each individual item or component, while *system-level* parameterization applies a uniform set of parameters across all items or components. In *item-level* PPCS, the total number of required planning parameters is the product of the number of parameters per item and the total number of items. Conversely, *system-level* PPCS requires only a single set of parameters for the entire system. This distinction is crucial, as *system-level* parameterization significantly reduces the effort needed for maintaining accurate master data, thereby ensuring performance (Pansara 2023). While group-level parameterization reduces administrative overhead, it fails to capture critical BOM-level dynamics. This study shows that item-specific tuning adapts to local constraints and variability. By decoupling these parameters, we uncover the true performance potential of the investigated PPC systems — precision that is structurally unattainable with aggregate settings.

2.2 Material Requirements Planning

Material Requirements Planning (MRP) is a *push* PPCS developed by Orlicky (1975), where production planning and order release follow four *centrally* controlled steps: netting, lot sizing, backward scheduling, and BOM explosion, as detailed by Hopp and Spearman (2011). Because WIP is not explicitly restricted at these steps, MRP is classified as a *push* PPCS.

At the netting step, material quantities are determined by offsetting gross requirements – derived from an Master Production Schedule (MPS) or customer orders – against the current inventory, excluding safety stock to prevent depletion during planning, and incorporating scheduled receipts (Matsuura and Tsubone 1991). Since MRP utilizes information about customer orders and forecasts, it is characterized as a *demand-driven* PPCS. At the lot sizing step, the net requirements can be batched based on lot sizing policies to balance set-up and ordering effort against inventory holding (Yelle 1979). Two common lot-sizing policies in MRP are Fixed Order Quantity (FOQ) and Fixed Order Period (FOP). FOQ orders a fixed quantity (or its multiple), while FOP batches net requirements over predefined intervals. Planned start dates are then set by backward scheduling based on planned lead times, and the same steps are repeated during the BoM explosion for all dependent items down to the lowest level.

To perform these four steps, three *item-level* planning parameters are required: safety stock, lot size (with the chosen lot sizing policy), and planned lead time. Safety stock protects against shortages but increases inventory costs. Lot size balances setup effort and holding costs and affects setup frequency, batch occupation, and shop load. Planned lead time specifies the time to complete an order, including waiting caused by machine utilization and stochastic processing or setup times (Altendorfer 2019).

2.3 Reorder Point System

The Reorder Point System (RPS) is a pull PPCS, leveraging on the Economic Order Quantity model, which focuses on minimizing the inventory management costs, i.e., set-up and ordering effort against inventory holding, by optimizing order quantities at stock replenishment (Silver et al. 1998). At RPS, production planning and order release are decentralized for each item, based on a comparison between the reorder point and the inventory position (Vollmann et al. 1997). The inventory position is calculated as the current inventory level plus any scheduled receipts minus any backorders. Consequently, RPS authorizes *production* without leveraging demand information. If the inventory position falls below the reorder point, a production order is triggered based on the FOQ lot sizing policy, which specifies a predetermined quantity or a multiple of it (Seiringer et al. 2023).

The planning parameters in RPS are the reorder point and lot size, both determined at the item level. The reorder point must cover demand during replenishment time while accounting for uncertainties in demand and production. Additionally, RPS has a conceptual connection to the well-known PPCS Kanban, as discussed by Yang (1998). Kanban can be viewed as a subtype of RPS, where the reorder point equals the number of Kanban containers minus one, multiplied by the container size. It differs mainly through its visual card-based signaling to trigger production. Thus, although the focus at this publication is on RPS, Kanban principles remain closely related and relevant.

2.4 Constant Work in Progress

Spearman et al. (1990) introduced ConWIP as a pull-based alternative to Kanban, using a work-ahead-window and card-controlled release that ties WIP and the WIP-Cap to the number of production orders. Because this order-based WIP-Cap limits effective load balancing, Thüerer et al. (2019) proposed linking the WIP-Cap to workload measured in standard processing time, which substantially improved performance. Following this idea, our discussion also defines WIP and the WIP-Cap in terms of workload.

In ConWIP, planning is demand-driven, with net requirements based on MPS or customer orders. The MPS may apply lot-sizing rules to balance setup and holding costs. Orders are released only if their due date lies within the work-ahead window, which acts as a scheduling window and prevents premature releases, thereby controlling finished-goods inventory (FGI) (Bokor and Altendorfer 2024). Production

orders are prioritized by Earliest Due Date (EDD), and release is allowed only when shop-floor WIP is below the WIP-Cap. Released orders are then dispatched using the standard ConWIP rule, First-In-System-First-Out (Spearman et al. 1990).

Both planning parameters (i.e., work-ahead window and WIP-Cap) apply uniformly across all items, providing the advantage of system-level parameterization (Spearman et al. 2022). However, as Jaegler et al. (2018), note, complex production structures may require additional, independently parameterized ConWIP loops to maintain performance. With two loops, planned start dates in the downstream loop (toward FGI) are set by backward scheduling using the estimated downstream lead time. The upstream start date is then determined by additional backward scheduling based on the upstream lead time. The earliest downstream start date follows from subtracting the work-ahead-window buffer from the planned start date; thus, the work-ahead window equals the estimated downstream lead time plus this buffer. For multiple ConWIP loops, three system-level parameters are required per loop: the work-ahead-window buffer, the WIP-Cap, and the estimated lead time. When an order finishes at the last machine of a loop, the loop's WIP decreases by the workload – its standard processing time including setup (Huang et al. 2015).

2.5 Summary PPCS classification

Table 1 summarizes the four key characteristics of the three PPCSs. The variable n denotes the number of items or components that must be parameterized when item-level settings are used. As n grows, the number of possible parameter combinations increases exponentially, substantially raising the number of simulation experiments required for planning-parameter optimization (Gansterer et al. 2014). As noted earlier, complex production systems may require additional independently parameterized ConWIP loops, which increases the number of system parameters proportionally to the number of loops.

Table 1: Characteristics of investigated PPCS.

	MRP	RPS	ConWIP
1. Operational mechanism	push	pull	pull
2. Demand orientation	demand-driven	authorizing production	demand-driven
3. Control structure	centralized	decentralized	centralized
4. Planning complexity / Parameters	item-level / $3n$	item-level / $2n$	system-level / 3 (per loop)

2.6 Simulation-Based Parameter Optimization

Jeon and Kim (2016) survey narrowed roughly 2,250 papers to 131 key studies and identified system dynamics, discrete-event simulation, and agent-based simulation as the main techniques for PPCS analysis. They also grouped the addressed issues into eight categories, such as scheduling and inventory management, offering guidance on selecting suitable simulation methods

Despite their value, simulation-based methods face challenges such as high computational effort, large problem scales, and uncertainty in both objectives and constraints. Stochastic models require many replications, making simulation optimization especially expensive (He et al. 2010). Full factorial designs become impractical as factors and levels grow, leading to exponential increases in required simulations (Law 2014; Seiringer et al. 2022a). As Nguyen et al. (2014) note, choosing suitable optimization methods – local vs. global, heuristic vs. metaheuristic – is essential. Simheuristics offer a promising way forward by embedding simulation within heuristic or metaheuristic search, making them well suited for complex stochastic combinatorial problems (Rabe et al. 2020).

Several studies have used simheuristics to optimize PPCS planning parameters. For RPS, Braglia et al. (2011) optimized reorder points and lot sizes using a genetic algorithm with a data-driven mutation operator and neighborhood search. For ConWIP, Framinan et al. (2003) distinguished between setting a fixed WIP-Cap and dynamically controlling it; most simheuristics address the latter. Early work such as Hopp and Roof's (1998) Statistical Throughput Control adjusted ConWIP cards based on throughput and lead-time thresholds and proved effective across diverse system settings. Pierreval et al. (2013) extended threshold-

based control by adding mechanisms to limit frequent card adjustments, improving stability and customer service. Complementary work has investigated simulation-based optimization methods. Simulated annealing has been used with Monte Carlo simulation in single-machine scheduling, whereas here it is embedded in a discrete-event simulation for PPCS parameter optimization (Bittencourt et al. 2025)

Nonetheless, most simheuristic research on planning-parameter optimization has focused on MRP, particularly on safety stock and planned lead times. Barrios et al. (2020) optimized safety stock by combining a heuristic for selecting promising configurations with simulation to estimate costs and variability, achieving balanced solutions that outperformed extreme settings. Karder et al. (2020) optimized all three planning parameters using two efficient global optimization variants. Their multi-objective, asynchronous approach achieved comparable solution quality to the traditional single-objective version while reducing runtime through parallel evaluations. Finite-capacity MRP has likewise been studied using hybrid metaheuristics under a lot-for-lot policy, with simulated annealing suggested for further improvement (Sukkerd and Wuttiornpun 2016).

Implementing and tuning simulation-based optimization can be complex. Seiringer et al. (2021) applied a simheuristic to optimize safety stock and planned lead time in a stochastic multi-item, multi-stage system, using simulated annealing with triangular sampling (LB, UB, mode) and updating the mode whenever a better solution was found. Seiringer et al. (2022a) later extended this approach by refining the search-space logic, integrating biased randomization (Ferone et al. 2019; Panadero et al. 2020) to escape local minima, and adding SBM, which reallocates replications from poor solutions to more promising ones. To assess SBM’s reliability, Seiringer et al. (2022b) tested different LB/UB settings on two production systems and showed that all settings identified the same optimal solution as full enumeration while reducing the simulation budget by up to ~70%. Bokor et al. (2025) confirmed these results for Drum-Buffer-Rope systems across nine environments, again finding identical optimal solutions and similar budget savings.

Building on these contributions, our simulation study applies a simheuristic to optimize all planning parameters of MRP, RPS, and ConWIP with the objective of minimizing overall costs. This makes the study well suited for stochastic combinatorial PPC parameter optimization. We evaluate multiple simulation budgets to assess whether additional budget improves solution quality – an important question when limited computation time may justify accepting lower-quality solutions. The simheuristic refines the search space using biased randomization to escape local minima and a simple statistics-based mechanism to allocate computational effort efficiently, in line with general simheuristic principles (Grasas et al. 2017).

3 SIMULATION MODEL

This section details the simulation model evaluating MRP, RPS, and ConWIP across flow, job, and hybrid shops. To replicate realistic manufacturing, the model incorporates stochastic multi-item and multi-stage behavior. Key elements include uncertainties in customer demand (arrivals, quantities, and due dates) and production processing (setup and processing times), alongside PPCS-specific mechanisms. Together, these provide a robust framework for assessing system effectiveness across diverse scenarios.

3.1 Production System

Three production system structures (Figure 1) are evaluated in this study: flow shop, job shop and hybrid shop. Each production system structure consists of eight items $\{101, \dots, 108\}$, each contributing a specific proportion to the total demand, represented by the following proportions: $\{0.100, 0.075, 0.200, 0.125, 0.075, 0.150, 0.150, 0.125\}$ for the i^{th} item, i.e., for the first item 0.100 and so on. In addition, the flow and hybrid shop structures include three components $\{201, 202, 301\}$. Each item, as well as components at lower levels, requires one component from the preceding level. However, processing an item or component may involve multiple machines at the same BoM level. The lowest BoM level in each production system corresponds to the item, while the highest level represents the raw material, which is always available and not planned.

Figure 1: Investigated production system structures with BoM: a) flow shop; b) job shop; c) hybrid shop

As shown in Figure 1 a), the flow shop structure features four machines spanning four BoM levels, with divergence occurring at both BoM Level 2 and BoM Level 1 as the process approaches the final item. At BoM Level 1, two machines are required to produce components 201 and 202. Figure 1 b) illustrates the job shop structure, which involves four machines and two BoM levels. Since BoM Level 1 represents raw materials in the job shop structure, only BoM Level 0 is planned. This level functions analogously to BoM Level 0 in the hybrid shop. In the job shop, however, up to four machines are available for processing, with item-specific routing determining which subset of machines is actually utilized. Figure 1 c) illustrates the hybrid shop configuration. It comprises six machines arranged across the four BoM levels and exhibits a comparable degree of routing divergence.

It starts with a flow shop material flow but transitions into a job shop production system at BoM Level 0, where the production path becomes item-specific, and not all machines are required for processing. The sequence of machines at BoM Level 0 is indicated by green-bordered letters, starting with 'A'.

Finally, these three production system structures strike a balance between simplicity, ensuring computational feasibility for the simulation study, and complexity, allowing for a thorough discussion of results based on their distinct characteristics. By encompassing varying levels of workflow rigidity and flexibility, they provide a comprehensive foundation for analyzing PPCS performance across diverse manufacturing scenarios, highlighting the interplay between system structure and operational efficiency.

While the model environment is based on a stylized set of eight items, this level of complexity was deliberately chosen to ensure the internal validity of the multi-stage interactions. In larger, empirical datasets, the structural effects of parameter decoupling are often obscured by statistical noise and system specific data variances. By utilizing a controlled 8-item structure, we can isolate and precisely analyze how item-level parameterization compensates for stage-specific bottlenecks and variability within the BOM. Following the principle of "parsimonious modeling" (Pidd 2009), this approach provides clear managerial guidance (Little 1970) on fundamental PPC mechanics before scaling to industrial systems. As per Law (2014), limiting the item set ensures high internal validity, isolating structural effects that large-scale empirical noise might otherwise mask. These items are mapped onto flow, job, and hybrid shop archetypes to capture multi-stage BOM dependencies and complex routing logic common in ERP modules (Vollmann et al. 2005). By generalizing these shop floor structures, the study remains representative of industrial planning logic, offering scalable insights tested within the same structural constraints that govern real-world manufacturing.

3.2 Customer Demand

To introduce demand uncertainty this study mirrors the customer behavior modeled by Felberbauer and Altendorfer (2014). Customer demand is characterized by stochastic interarrival times, stochastic customer order quantities and a stochastic customer required lead time (CRL). The arrival of customer orders follows a lognormal distribution with an expected mean of \mathcal{B} customer orders per day and a coefficient of variation (CV) of 0.2 . Each customer order consists of a single item type. To assess the impact of planned shop load levels on PPCS performance, the expected mean customer order quantities for the eight items are adjusted, leading to planned shop loads of 85% , 90% , and 93% (represented as $\in \{0.85, 0.90, 0.93\}$). However, the proportionality among items remains constant, as detailed in Section 3.1. To further increase demand uncertainty, the actual order quantities for these eight items also follow a lognormal distribution with a CV of 0.2 . Additionally, the CRL itself contains uncertainty, integrating both a fixed and variable portion to ensure a minimum time for production. To investigate the influence of due date tightness on PPCS performance, two scenarios are analyzed: a tight and a relaxed due date environment. In the tight due date scenario, the fixed proportion is set to 0 days and the expected mean to 10 days, representing a stringent delivery requirement. In the relaxed scenario, both the fixed proportion and the expected mean are set to 10 days, reflecting more flexible delivery conditions.

3.3 Production Planning

The production planning mechanisms differ across the three PPCSs, as outlined in Section 2. Table 2 summarizes the corresponding model settings, covering the production system, customer demand, each PPCS's planning logic, and the production-order processing details.

For MRP, planned lead time, lot size, and safety stock are set at the item or component level, allowing distinct planning parameters for each. Whereby, the planned lead times are set in days, the FOP lot sizing measured in days is applied and safety stock levels are set as a proportion of the expected mean customer order quantities per day, or for components, as the sum of the demands of items requiring that component. For example, setting a safety stock level of 2 for an item with an expected demand of 50 items per day results in a total safety stock of 100 pieces.

For RPS, the reorder point and lot size are also set at the item or component level. The FOQ lot sizing policy is applied, following the standard configuration, and both parameters are determined using a similar ratio-based logic on the proportion of the expected mean customer order quantities. As a result, for both MRP and RPS in the flow shop and hybrid shop production systems, parameters are optimized separately for 8 items and 3 components, while in the job shop production system, the 8 items are individually optimized.

For ConWIP, an MPS is implemented using FOQ lot sizing policy to aggregate demand. Lot sizes are set as a proportion of the expected mean customer order quantities. WIP and the WIP-Cap are expressed in workload minutes based on the expected mean setup and processing times. In the flow shop and hybrid shop, where the BoM includes two levels, two ConWIP loops are implemented as recommended by recommended Huang et al. (2015): a downstream loop for items and an upstream loop for components. Planned start dates are set via backward scheduling using the estimated upstream lead times. Early release is allowed through a work-ahead window defined as the downstream lead time plus a buffer.

In the job shop, which operates with a single ConWIP loop, planning parameters consist of FOQ, WIP-Cap, and the estimated downstream lead time, whereas the flow and hybrid shops require two additional parameters for the upstream loop: the estimated upstream lead time and the work-ahead-window buffer.

3.4 Production Order Processing

Demand generation applies customer-required lead times (CRL) to determine customer due dates, which correspond to the planned end dates of production orders; production orders are then released according to the Earliest Due Date (EDD) rule based on these planned end dates and follow item- or component-specific production paths across all three PPCSs. During shop floor processing setup and processing times are

lognormally distributed with a CV of 0.2. Mean setup times are standardized at the machine level and identical across items and components, with total setup time representing 10% of capacity under a lot-for-lot policy. In contrast, mean processing times differ by item or component and by machine. Because CV is defined at the single piece level for item/component, overall production order processing-time uncertainty decreases with increasing lot size. Finished goods remain in FGI until their customer due date, and any tardy orders are shipped immediately upon completion.

Table 2 summarizes the simulation model, including the production system structure, customer demand, planning mechanisms (MRP, RPS, ConWIP), and order processing. The model contains two main sources of uncertainty: customer demand and production order processing. Customer-demand uncertainty stems from interarrival times, order quantities, and the variable CRL component. Processing uncertainty arises from setup and processing times. All stochastic variables follow lognormal distributions due to their non-negativity and common use in prior work.

Table 2: Overview simulation model details.

Category	Details
Production System	
Production system structure	Flow shop; Hybrid shop; Job shop
Number of items/components	8 items (Flow/Hybrid/Job- shop) / 3 components (Flow/Hybrid- shop)
Proportion of demand for the i^{th} item	$i^{th} = \{0.100, 0.075, 0.200, 0.125, 0.075, 0.150, 0.150, 0.125\}$
Customer Demand	
Interarrival time of customer orders [per day]	$E = 0.125, CV = 0.2$ (LogNorm)
Customer order quantities	Dependent on planned shop load $\{0.85, 0.90, 0.93\}$, $CV = 0.2$ (LogNorm)
Fixed portion of CRL [days]	0 (Tight); 10 (Relaxed)
Variable portion of CRL [days]	$E = 10, SD = 2$ (Tight & Relaxed); (LogNorm)
Production Planning	
MRP	Item-/component specific {planned lead time, FOP lot size, safety stock}
RPS	Item-/component specific {reorder point, FOQ lot size}
ConWIP	MPS FOQ lot size, WIP-Cap, downstream/upstream estimated lead time, work-ahead-window buffer
Production Order Processing	
Release mechanism	Based on planned start dates
Dispatching rule	FIFO for MRP/RPS; FISFO for ConWIP
Setup time	Standardized across machines, $E \approx 10\%$ of available time, $CV = 0.2$ (LogNorm)
Processing time	Item-/component and machine specific, $CV = 0.2$ (LogNorm)

4 NUMERICAL STUDY SETUP

This section presents the numerical study setup to evaluate MRP, RPS and ConWIP using the described simheuristic for parameter optimization including pre-simulation study results used to set starting parameterizations for the simheuristic. During the numerical study with the simheuristic, planning parameters are optimized for each PPCS within each production system environment and at each simulation budget level. Given the three production system structures (flow shop, job shop, and hybrid shop), three planned shop loads (0.85, 0.90, 0.93), and two due date tightness levels (tight and relaxed), this leads to a total of 18 distinct production system environments. In total, evaluating the three PPCS across 18 production system environments and three different simulation budget levels results in 162 simulation experiments.

Compared to of Seiringer et al. (2024), this study removes earlier uniform parameter restrictions. Previously, one set of parameters applied to all items, another to all components, and identical WIP-Caps were used for both ConWIP loops. In the current study, item- and component-specific planning parameters are set for MRP and RPS, while loop-specific parameters are used for ConWIP, exponentially enlarging the search space. Each independent parameter choice multiplies the number of possible configurations (see Table 1).

Given this exponentially growing search space, full enumeration becomes computationally impractical. Consequently, a simheuristic-based optimization approach was implemented to effectively explore the complex decision landscape. As the performance of the simheuristic depends on the initial values, a preliminary experiment was conducted to obtain meaningful starting values for the large performance comparison and to increase its relevance by ensuring a well-founded and fair evaluation.

4.1 Simulation Model Framework

The simulation procedure shown in Figure 2 is implemented in AnyLogic using an agent-based model that captures all required behaviors from demand generation to stock keeping. The framework employs an SQLite database to store the production system setup and can be configured for multi-item and multi-stage production systems as used in the simulation experiments. Based on the provided BoM and routing data, the simulation automatically generates the agent instances for each run. To accelerate the simulation experiments, the workload can be distributed across multiple client machines. Each client retrieves pending parameterizations from a database and returns the computed KPIs after each iteration, enabling efficient parallel execution and reducing overall computation time.

Figure 2: Overview of the simulation procedure for evaluating production planning and control systems

The general flow of the simulation procedure in Figure 2 illustrates, how the performance of MRP, RPS, and ConWIP is evaluated within a rolling-horizon setting. Scenario parameters define the experimental setup, including the production system configuration (BoM and routing information), simulation runtime, warm-up phase, planning method (MRP, RPS, ConWIP), simheuristic configuration, maximum number of replications per iteration, and planning horizon (in days). Demand generation, order release, and shop floor processing are governed by the rules described in Section 3.4, whereas the stock-keeping process is responsible for managing inventories of components and finished goods. During execution, the simheuristic module dynamically updates production planning parameters after each iteration and may skip subsequent replications within an iteration if the current iteration's average cost lies outside the percentile range of the best-performing solutions. The following key performance indicators (KPIs) were identified as most relevant: service level, tardiness, utilization, work in process, and inventory levels.

4.2 Simheuristic Methodology

The applied simheuristic follows a simulation-based search procedure that combines iterative parameter sampling with stochastic performance evaluation. Building on the developments in Seiringer et al. (2021), Seiringer et al. (2022a) and Seiringer et al. (2022b), the simulation framework was re-engineered to transition from aggregate item-grouping to high-dimensional, item-specific parameterization. This architectural shift enables the simheuristic to simultaneously tune individual parameters across the multi-stage BOM, navigating a significantly more complex decision space than earlier versions of the framework. The simheuristic integrates three components: Simulated Annealing (SA) for solution acceptance, Simulation Budget Management (SBM) for adaptive replication control, and Exponential Range Reduction (ERR) for progressively narrowing the parameter bounds during the search.

During initialization, the algorithm samples an initial parameter configuration from a triangular distribution and evaluates it with the maximum number of replications. Each iteration then simulates a new configuration, applies SBM to determine whether further replications should be conducted, and uses SA to decide whether the configuration becomes the new base or even the best solution. Once the warm-up threshold is exceeded, ERR narrows the parameter bounds – either when a new best solution is identified or when SBM signals sufficient sampling progress – focusing the search on promising regions while maintaining adequate exploration. Pseudocodes of all four components, together with Table 7 summarizing all variables, are provided in the appendix. This section offers a textual description of the simheuristic, while Algorithm 1 outlines the overall flow and the interaction between its components. The detailed mechanisms of SBM, SA, and ERR are presented in the appendix as Algorithms 2–4.

The SBM mechanism – see Algorithm 2 in the Appendix, originally introduced in Seiringer et al. (2022b) and also applied in Bokor et al. (2025) is slightly improved. To increase its robustness, two extensions were implemented: (1) a global overall-cost limit derived from preliminary experiments, which acts as an additional early-stop criterion independent of the percentile rule, and (2) exclusion of zero-cost values from the percentile computation, since skipped replications are included in the result set and would otherwise distort the statistical comparison. After the warm-up phase, SBM evaluates the non-zero average costs of previous iterations, computes a percentile threshold based on the dynamically adjusted percentile position p , and compares it with the mean cost of replications completed so far in the current iteration. If this mean exceeds the threshold, the remaining replications are skipped. A potential range reduction (ERR) is triggered only after reaching the maximum number of replications per iteration ($maxReps$), i.e., once the solution value has been classified by SBM as lying within the acceptable percentile bounds.

The Algorithm 3 in the appendix presents a compact SA acceptance rule enriched with credit-based biased randomization inspired by the demon algorithm (Juan et al. 2014). After resetting the SA state when required, improvements are always accepted, and new global best solutions trigger a full SA reset. Worse solutions may still be accepted when the credit balance allows it, enabling controlled diversification and escape from local minima. The function returns whether the solution was accepted and whether it constitutes a new best.

The final component, ERR, shown in Algorithm 4 of the appendix, contracts each parameter’s bounds toward the midpoint of the current best solution using an iteration-dependent shrink factor while enforcing a relative minimum gap of the initial range. Shrinking is triggered only when a new best solution is identified, preventing premature restriction of the search space. Compared to the earlier approach in Seiringer et al. (2022a), where bounds were not systematically defined and the smaller number of iterations implicitly avoided over-narrowing, the current implementation initializes lb , ub , and $mode$ based on a preliminary simulation study and applies feasibility corrections by rounding and enforcing bounds on sampled values. ERR was further adapted to ensure stable bounds even under a global simulation budget of 10,000 replications, which is now tracked cumulatively across iterations. These adaptations yield a controlled, stable narrowing of the search region while preserving sufficient variability for continued exploration.

4.3 Simheuristic and Simulation Settings

Following the conceptual description, this subsection outlines the experimental configuration, including parameters for SBM, SA, and ERR and the simulation setup. Table 3 summarizes these settings.

The simheuristic begins with a warm-up phase of 50 iterations ($warmupIter$). The initial values for each planning parameter p – that is, the triangular-distribution bounds $lb[p]$, $ub[p]$, and the mode – are derived from a preliminary experiment (see Section 4.4). The minimum gap $minGap$, to which $lb[p]$ and $ub[p]$ are gradually reduced, is deliberately set to the very small threshold of 0.0001. This allows the bounds to shrink as far as practically possible while preserving numerical stability and sufficient local variability. In our experiments, this small gap supported an exhaustive exploration of the parameter space, although larger values may be preferable in other contexts.

For SA, the reset frequency (*defaultSAReset*), used to escape unpromising regions of the search space, is set to 5. The SBM algorithm starts after 5 iterations, with the number of replications per iteration ranging between *minReps* = 3 and *maxReps* = 20. The percentile-based threshold calculation uses lower and upper bounds of 0.02 and 0.2 (*SBMlb*, *SBMub*).

The best-performing value from the preliminary study defines the mode of the triangular distribution, while the lower and upper bounds are obtained by subtracting or adding the parameter-specific *lb/ub* factors listed in Table 4. These bounds were selected to match the simulation budget and to stay within meaningful ranges, avoiding unrealistic extremes. Table 4 also specifies step sizes, rounding rules (integer or half-integer), and minimum feasible values (e.g., preventing FOP = 0). For instance, the MRP lead-time range {1, 3, 5} uses an *lb/ub* factor of ± 3 and a step size of 1. If a lead time of 3 yields the lowest cost, the resulting bounds become *lb* = 1 and *ub* = 6, and the simheuristic adjusts this parameter in integer steps after triangular sampling.

To ensure fair comparison and avoid favouring systems with larger search spaces (e.g., MRP), three simulation-budget levels are used: 1,000 (low), 3,000 (medium), and 10,000 (high) total replications.

The higher dimensionality of item-level systems (MRP, RPS) theoretically complicates the search compared to system-level ConWIP. From a search-space complexity perspective, these high-dimensional systems might require larger budgets for full convergence. However, to ensure a fair comparison under practical constraints, we apply identical simulation budgets to all PPC systems. This evaluates which approach is most effective when computational effort is a finite resource.

The simulation uses a total runtime of 500 days with an 85-day warm-up period. This compensates for the empty initial state, which would otherwise disadvantage ConWIP relative to MRP and RPS, whose safety stocks and reorder points act as initial buffers. Customer-order arrivals stop after day 450 to ensure that the system can naturally empty before the experiment ends. This setup allows all PPCS to reach a representative operating state before KPI collection, while keeping the overall runtime computationally efficient.

The simulation workload is distributed across 22 PCs equipped with Intel Core i5-10500 processors (six cores) and 32 GB RAM. Multiple simulation instances are executed in parallel on each PC, which substantially accelerates the overall experiment.

To evaluate overall performance, production–logistics cost components associated with WIP, FGI, and tardiness are aggregated. Raw material costs are set to 66.40 cost units (CU) per component, and a 100% value-added markup is applied, resulting in a manufacturing cost of 132.80 CU per finished item. An annual carrying charge rate of 7% is assumed.

Based on these assumptions, the resulting cost structure assigns increasing economic weight to later production stages and customer delay. All daily cost rates are normalized to the evaluated simulation horizon of 415 days (excluding the warm-up period). WIP components, inventory components, and WIP items each incur 0.0112 CU per unit per day, while finished-goods inventory incurs 0.0224 CU per unit per day. Tardiness is penalized at 0.4256 CU per item per day, representing a substantially higher cost to emphasize service-level performance. WIP components denote unfinished items at BoM levels other than Level 0, whereas WIP items refer to work-in-process at BoM Level 0 corresponding to finished goods. The tardiness cost is derived from a target service level of 95%, calculated as $\text{service level} = 1 - (FGI \text{ costs}) / (FGI \text{ costs} + \text{tardiness costs})$, following Axsäter (2015). Items that are late and not delivered by the end of the simulation are accounted for based on their current lateness, ensuring their impact on overall performance is reflected. For simplicity, transportation costs for intralogistics material handling are not included. This approach ensures that the penalty schema is not arbitrary but reflects a common managerial decision context, where the penalty represents the opportunity cost of failing to meet customer expectations. To further validate the results, a sensitivity analysis was conducted by varying the tardiness penalty by $\pm 50\%$. The relative ranking of the evaluated PPCS remained unchanged, confirming that the findings reflect the structural capabilities of the systems rather than being sensitive to the specific cost weighting.

Table 3: Applied simheuristic and simulation experiment.

ERR with SA and SBM simheuristic setting		Agent-based discrete event simulation setting	
Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Warm-up phase [iterations]	50	Simulation time [days]	500
Initial parameters triangular distribution $lb[p], ub[p], mid[p]$	specific	Warm-up time [days]	85
Minimum parameter gap $minGap$	0.0001	WIP component costs [CU per day]	0.0112
Initial value $defaultSAReset$	5	Inventory component costs [CU per day]	0.0112
Number of $startingIterations$	5	WIP item costs [CU per day]	0.0112
Number of $minReps$	3	FGI costs [CU per day]	0.0224
Number of $maxReps$	20	Tardiness costs [CU per day]	0.4256
$SBMub$	0.2	Starting inventory	No
$SBMlb$	0.02	Parallel computing	Yes
Simulation budget [in Tsd. replications]	{1, 3, 10}	Simulation runtime [sec. per run]	~5

4.4 Preliminary Experiment for Initial Parametrization

To determine the initial planning parameters for the 18 production system environments, a preliminary experiment was conducted. To ensure a fair comparison among the PPCS, an approximately equal number of simulation runs were performed, applying identical planning parameters across all items, components, and respective ConWIP loops. Table 4 summarizes the ranges based on preliminary results from Seiringer et al. (2024), extended by lb/ub, step size, and minimum lb.

To ensure statistical robustness, 20 replications per iteration were conducted across 18 environments. This resulted in: 9,720 runs for MRP (27 iterations), 9,000 for RPS (25 iterations), and 11,520 for ConWIP (32 iterations).

Table 4: Initial parameter ranges and settings for simheuristic.

	Planning parameter	Initial parameters tested	Factor lb/ub	Step size	Min. value
MRP	Planned lead time [days]	{1, 3, 5}	-/+ 3	1	1
	FOP lot size [days]	{1, 3, 5}	-/+ 2	1	1
	Safety stock [prop. demand]	{0, 1, 2}	-/+ 1	0.5	0
RPS	Reorder-point [prop. demand]	{5, 6, 7, 8, 9}	-/+ 2	0.5	1
	FOQ lot size [prop. demand]	{1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0}	-/+ 1.5	0.5	0.5
ConWIP	MPS FOQ lot size [prop. demand]	{1.0, 2.0, 3.0}	-/+ 1.5	0.5	0.5
	WIP-Cap [workload in Tsd. minutes]	{60, 90, 120}	-/+ 20	1	20
	Estimated lead time [days]	{3, 6, 9}	-/+ 3	1	1
	Work-ahead-window buffer [days]	1	-/+ 1	1	0

4.5 Preliminary Experiment Result Analysis

Table 5a/5b summarizes the minimum overall costs and associated parameter settings of the pre-simulation study. The analysis covers the three production-system structures (Flow Shop, Job Shop, and Hybrid Shop), three planned shop loads (0.85, 0.90, 0.93), and the production-control policies (MRP, RPS, ConWIP), each examined under two due-date settings (“Tight” and “Relaxed”). The results reveal a complex interaction between due-date pressure, utilization, and planning approach — no single configuration dominates across all settings.

Under tight due dates (Table 5a), overall costs rise with utilization across all structure–policy combinations as congestion intensifies, consistent with the congestion-driven cost increases discussed by Dang et al. (2022). In the Flow Shop, MRP performs best at low utilization, ConWIP at medium, and RPS

at high. In the Job Shop, ConWIP consistently yields the lowest costs, followed by RPS and MRP, aligning with Romagnoli (2015), who shows that ConWIP reduces WIP and flow-time variability in real job shops. In the Hybrid Shop, MRP dominates at low load, ConWIP at medium, and RPS at high. Cost variability also increases with utilization.

With due dates relaxed by ten days (Table 5b), overall costs still rise with utilization across all production systems, consistent with Pinedo (2022), but the relative performance of the planning approaches shifts. In the Flow Shop, MRP performs best at low load, ConWIP at medium, and MRP again at high load, reflecting the alternating push–pull advantage noted by (Thiagarajan and Rajendran 2005). In the Job Shop, MRP is slightly better at low utilization, while ConWIP becomes most cost-efficient as load increases. In the Hybrid Shop, MRP dominates across all load levels. As for tight due dates, cost variability decreases under relaxed due dates, aligning with Stevenson et al. (2005) and Enns (1995).

Tables 5a and 5b show that parameter values generally increase with higher load, reflecting the model’s adjustment to growing congestion through larger planning settings, consistent with lot-sizing and inventory theory (Drexel and Kimms 1997; Silver et al. 1998). For MRP, this appears as longer planned lead times and larger lot sizes, reflecting evidence that both parameters act as buffers against congestion and variability (Whybark and Williams 1976; Enns 1999, 2001, 2002). In RPS, rising utilization results in higher reorder points and lot sizes, consistent with (Q, r) theory, where increased demand or variability shifts optimal reorder levels upward (Silver et al. 1998; Chung et al. 2009). ConWIP requires only minor adjustments: its workload cap and work-ahead settings remain largely stable across utilization levels, with slight increases only at the highest load (Jodlbauer and Huber 2008; Braglia et al. 2011).

RPS results are nearly identical across due-date regimes, production systems, and utilization levels. This reflects its inventory-driven logic, where releases depend on stock positions rather than due dates, making it largely insensitive to due-date tightness (Silver et al. 1998). From a modeling standpoint, this confirms that replenishment decisions are governed by reorder points instead of future demand information.

The consistency across production systems and due-date settings suggests that the pre-simulation ranges were already near optimal, leaving only marginal improvements, consistent with the robustness of PPC parameters Kleijnen and Gaury (2003) and limited gains beyond near-optimal schedules (Luh et al. 1997). These results therefore provide a well-calibrated baseline for the subsequent simheuristic evaluation.

Table 5a: Minimum Overall Costs and Parameterization of Pre-Simulation Study (Tight Setting).

Env.	Due date tightness Production system structure Planned shop load	Tight [0 days fix + E[10] days variable CRL]								
		Flow Shop			Job Shop			Hybrid Shop		
		0.85	0.90	0.93	0.85	0.90	0.93	0.85	0.90	0.93
MRP	Overall costs [CU]	21,983	34,851	59,647	13,951	43,422	91,666	23,078	39,476	91,339
	Overall costs STD [CU]	785	354	22,522	815	9,926	72,400	952	2,465	30,110
	Planned lead time [days]	1	3	3	5	5	5	3	3	3
	FOP lot size [days]	1	3	3	1	3	3	1	3	3
	Safety stock [prop. demand]	2	2	2	0	2	2	1	2	2
RPS	Overall costs [CU]	38,951	43,016	46,898	31,377	45,016	86,064	40,950	44,939	49,399
	Overall costs STD [CU]	431	748	1,520	2,210	11,331	66,225	801	1,111	2,360
	Reorder-point [prop. demand]	5	5	6	9	9	9	6	6	7
	FOQ lot size [prop. demand]	1	1	1	1	3	3	1	1	1
ConWIP	Overall costs [CU]	24,138	32,827	70,563	17,117	27,670	53,869	24,151	35,515	99,189
	Overall costs STD [CU]	739	7,427	18,101	295	12,038	65,675	1,173	7,868	31,143
	MPS FOQ lot size [prop. demand]	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2
	Estimated lead time [days]	3	3	3	6	6	9	3	3	3
	WIP-Cap [workload in minutes]	60,000	60,000	60,000	60,000	60,000	120,000	60,000	60,000	60,000
	Work-ahead-window buffer [days]	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1

Table 5b: Minimum Overall Costs and Parameterization of Pre-Simulation Study (Relaxed Setting).

Env.	Due date tightness Production system structure Planned shop load	Relaxed [10 days fix + E[10] days variable CRL]								
		Flow Shop			Job Shop			Hybrid Shop		
		0.85	0.90	0.93	0.85	0.90	0.93	0.85	0.90	0.93
MRP	Overall costs [CU]	19,110	32,933	40,278	14,012	44,638	91,738	18,493	33,402	38,493
	Overall costs STD [CU]	116	13,670	426	851	9,893	67,595	165	2,143	398
	Planned lead time [days]	3	3	5	5	5	5	3	3	5
	FOP lot size [days]	1	1	3	1	3	3	1	1	3
	Safety stock [prop. demand]	0	1	0	0	2	2	0	2	0
RPS	Overall costs [CU]	38,951	43,016	46,898	31,377	45,016	86,064	40,950	44,939	49,399
	Overall costs STD [CU]	431	748	1,520	2,210	11,331	66,225	801	1,111	2,360
	Reorder-point [prop. demand]	5	5	6	9	9	9	6	6	7
	FOQ lot size [prop. demand]	1	1	1	1	3	3	1	1	1
ConWIP	Overall costs [CU]	25,025	30,012	49,504	17,210	27,579	48,957	25,034	36,278	48,492
	Overall costs STD [CU]	521	3,587	327	359	10,951	54,842	907	6,221	8,309
	MPS FOQ lot size [prop. demand]	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	1
	Estimated lead time [days]	3	3	6	6	6	9	3	3	6
	WIP-Cap [workload in minutes]	60,000	60,000	60,000	60,000	60,000	120,000	60,000	60,000	60,000
	Work-ahead-window buffer [days]	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1

5 NUMERICAL RESULTS

This section presents the results of applying the simheuristic described in Section 4.2 for the introduced numerical study. We first compare the performance of the three PPCS across utilizations and both due-date settings. The analysis begins with results obtained under the maximum simulation budget of 10,000 iterations, followed by a comparison of solution quality over iterations. We then examine performance under different simulation budgets and replication run times, and provide a sensitivity analysis identifying the best-performing PPCS across all tested settings. Finally, we discuss the planning parameters of the simheuristic for the resulting best configurations.

5.1 Simheuristic Performance of PPCS for Flow Shop, Job Shop and Hybrid Shop

Figures 3a–5b compare the relative cost composition (inventory + WIP and tardiness shares) and absolute overall cost values (secondary Y-axis). The silver line represents overall costs without heuristic, and the orange line those with the applied simheuristic., ConWIP, MRP, and RPS are evaluated across three utilization levels (0.85, 0.90, 0.93) and shop structures (Flow, Job, Hybrid) using a simulation budget of 10,000 replications. Each figure pair contrasts tight and relaxed customer lead-time settings. The PPCS with the lowest overall costs is highlighted by a red line beneath the planning method name.

Looking at Figures 3a–5b the performance patterns from the pre-simulation study also hold in the simheuristic evaluation: rising utilization drives congestion, policy rankings shift with shop structure and load, and RPS remains stable but less flexible – consistent with established PPCS behavior (Spearman et al. 1990; Silver et al. 1998; Romagnoli 2015). Since the baseline parameter settings in Table 5a/5b were already near-optimal and lie in robust regions (Luh et al. 1997; Kleijnen and Gaury 2003), the simheuristic mainly provides targeted refinements rather than large structural shifts. Based on these baseline settings, the results show how much extra improvement the simheuristic adds and which PPCS benefit most. Despite strong initial settings, applying the simheuristic and thereby increasing parameter search space consistently improves performance:

Across all production systems and both due-date settings, the simheuristic achieves lower overall costs compared with the pre-simulation baseline shown in Table 5a and Table 5b. Effects range from marginal with 2.2% (e.g., Flow Shop, tight CRL 0, utilization 0.85, MRP – 21,193 CU vs. 20,737 CU) to substantial with 60% (e.g., Flow Shop, tight CRL 0, utilization 0.93 ConWIP — 70,563 CU vs. 28,238 CU) and become more pronounced with higher utilization, particularly in the Job Shop. The smallest improvement amounts to 936 CU (6.71 %) for MRP at 0.85 utilization (tight CRL 0, Job Shop). Averaged across all configurations, cost reductions reach 23.3 % for MRP, 8.1 % for RPS, and 25.2 % for ConWIP. These improvements are

consistent with prior evidence that simheuristic-based search can refine already good parameter settings and outperform static configurations (Pichitlamken and Nelson 2003; Kleijnen 2015).

Figure 3a: Flow Shop tight CRL

Figure 3b: Flow Shop relaxed CRL

Figure 4a: Job Shop tight CRL

Figure 4b: Job Shop relaxed CRL

As in the pre-simulation study, no single PPCS dominates across all settings: ConWIP and MRP consistently achieve the lowest overall costs, with ConWIP showing the strongest gains and MRP performing better at lower utilization. RPS remains the most stable but least flexible approach; still, the simheuristic yields measurable cost reductions even under high-load and tight-lead-time conditions. Such robustness of improvements aligns with findings that simheuristics effectively exploit near-optimal regions and amplify small residual gaps in parameter landscapes (Chica et al. 2020).

Utilization remains the dominant performance driver: at 0.85 all systems operate stably with small differences among PPCS; at 0.90 mild congestion occurs; and at 0.93 tardiness and overall costs rise sharply, especially in Job and Hybrid Shops. Even under the highest load, the simheuristic identifies improved parameter settings and reduces overall costs. This demonstrates its ability to adapt planning parameters dynamically and extract performance gains even in highly congested environments.

Relaxing due-date tightness ($CRL = 10$) produces the expected trade-off: lower tardiness but higher WIP and inventory costs as orders are released and completed earlier. In the Flow Shop, an average tardiness share of 5.67 % shows little impact on overall costs. In the Job Shop, tardiness increases steeply with utilization (15.72 % \rightarrow 23.79 % \rightarrow 56.89 %), illustrating how routing complexity amplifies bottleneck effects. Hybrid Shop tardiness falls between Flow Shop and Job Shop levels, reflecting reduced delay propagation due to lower routing complexity.

These comparative patterns across shop structures, utilization levels, and due-date tightness directly address RQ1 by showing how each PPCS fits specific production environments: ConWIP performs best in structurally complex and highly utilized systems, MRP excels at lower loads or relaxed due dates, and RPS remains stable but less responsive to structural variation.

5.2 Solution Performance Relation to Iterations

After examining cost performance across PPCS and shop types, this section analyzes how improvements develop over the iterative search process, referencing solution quality directly to iteration count. The results are exemplified through Figures 6a–8b comparing Flow, Job, and Hybrid Shops under relaxed lead time setting and utilization levels of 0.85 and 0.93. Each iteration represents one full evaluation cycle in which a new parameter configuration is sampled, simulated with an SBM-controlled number of replications, and evaluated through the SA acceptance step. As SBM can stop early, the iteration count reflects search progress rather than fixed simulation effort.

Across all environments, solution quality improves during the search, with effects varying by structure and load. In the Flow Shop, gains are moderate at 0.85 utilization and much stronger at 0.93, where ConWIP shows steep early reductions. In the Job Shop, improvements are small at 0.85 but pronounced at 0.93, consistent with Chen and Lee (2010). In the Hybrid Shop, all PPCS improve, especially at 0.93. High congestion amplifies parameter effects, underscoring the practical value of simheuristic tuning in stochastic settings (Juan et al. 2015; Chica et al. 2020).

In summary, across all three shop structures, the simheuristic consistently improves solution quality, with the magnitude and timing of improvements depending strongly on utilization and system complexity. This aligns with well-known interaction patterns between search progress and stochastic performance landscapes in simulation-optimization (Andradottir 1998; Fu 2002). ConWIP achieves the largest and most consistent gains, while MRP improves more gradually – particularly under higher load. RPS converges early with only minor adjustments, reflecting typical differences in how metaheuristic search trajectories respond to landscape steepness and variance (April et al. 2003). These divergent trajectories also reflect the underlying tractability of the systems: the high-dimensional parameter space of item-level MRP requires significantly more iterations to navigate toward an optimum, whereas the lower dimensionality of ConWIP allows for more efficient search progress. Consequently, the simpler configurability of system-level parameters proves to be a strategic advantage under limited simulation budgets.

These dynamics address RQ2, showing that higher simulation budgets are most beneficial in highly congested, high-variability settings, where additional replications better distinguish between parameter configurations and enable more reliable search refinement.

Figure 6a: Flow Shop performance (CRL=10 (relaxed), utilization 0.85

Figure 6b: Flow Shop performance (CRL=10 (relaxed), utilization 0.93

Figure 7a: Job Shop performance (CRL=10 (relaxed), utilization 0.85

Figure 7b: Job Shop performance (CRL=10 (relaxed), utilization 0.93

Figure 8a: Hybrid Shop performance (CRL=10 (relaxed), utilization 0.85

Figure 8b: Hybrid Shop performance (CRL=10 (relaxed), utilization 0.93

5.3 Best-Performing PPC Systems across Production System Environments

While the previous analysis examined iteration-driven improvements within each PPCS, the following results compare PPCS performance across shop structures, utilization levels, customer-required lead times, and simulation budgets. Table 6 summarizes these comparative outcomes. Table 6 provides the results of simheuristic-based evaluation of the three PPCS systems across shop structures (Flow, Job, Hybrid), utilization levels (0.85, 0.90, 0.93), and customer-required lead-time settings (tight vs. relaxed). For each combination, the simheuristic identifies the best-performing PPCS under three simulation budget levels (1,000; 3,000; 10,000 replications), with * and ** denoting statistical significance at the 95% and 99% confidence levels. Significance is assessed relative to the second-best performing PPCS.

Overall, ConWIP delivers the most robust and cost-efficient performance across the three shop types, particularly at higher utilization levels where effective WIP regulation becomes critical, although its advantage varies across shop structures and load conditions (Spearman et al. 1990; Thüerer et al. 2012), a pattern that is also observed in analytical comparisons of WIP-controlled PPCS under deterministic conditions (Lee and Seo 2016).

The results reveal a clear pattern: MRP outperforms the other PPCS primarily at the 0.85 utilization level – both in the relaxed CRL settings across all shop types and in the tight CR. In the Hybrid Shop with relaxed CRL settings, MRP is best in 3 out of 9 evaluated cases, and all three exhibit statistical significance, demonstrating that MRP can surpass ConWIP and RPS under low congestion and less restrictive lead-time requirements. Outside these lowest utilization levels, MRP achieves the best performance in only two additional isolated settings, both occurring under tight CRL and 0.93 utilization – once in the Flow Shop and once in the Hybrid Shop. These results indicate that MRP can remain competitive even at higher shop loads, although ConWIP is favored in the vast majority of remaining cases. Increasing the simulation budget does not systematically alter or strengthen these significance patterns. Moreover, the convergence of results across all three simulation budgets demonstrates that the simheuristic reliably identifies the superior PPCS, indicating a stable and robust search process (Fu 2002; Chen and Lee 2010).

Table 6: Best-performing PPC systems identified by the simheuristic across shop structures, utilization levels, CRL settings, and three simulation budgets

		<i>Tight CRL</i>			<i>Relaxed CRL</i>		
		<i>(0 days fix + E[10] days variable)</i>			<i>(10 days fix + E[10] days variable)</i>		
		<i>Sim. Budget</i>	<i>Utilization</i>			<i>Utilization</i>	
		0.85	0.90	0.93	0.85	0.90	0.93
<i>Flow shop</i>	1,000	ConWIP**	ConWIP	MRP	MRP**	ConWIP**	ConWIP**
	3,000	ConWIP	ConWIP**	ConWIP*	MRP	ConWIP	ConWIP
	10,000	ConWIP**	ConWIP	ConWIP	MRP**	ConWIP	ConWIP
<i>Job shop</i>	1,000	MRP	ConWIP	ConWIP	MRP**	ConWIP	ConWIP
	3,000	MRP	ConWIP	ConWIP	MRP	ConWIP	ConWIP
	10,000	MRP	ConWIP	ConWIP	MRP	ConWIP	ConWIP
<i>Hybrid shop</i>	1,000	ConWIP	ConWIP	MRP**	MRP**	ConWIP**	ConWIP
	3,000	ConWIP	ConWIP	ConWIP	MRP**	ConWIP**	ConWIP
	10,000	ConWIP*	ConWIP	ConWIP	MRP**	ConWIP**	ConWIP

5.4 Impact of Simulation Budget on Overall Cost Estimates per PPCS

This subsection examines how increasing the simheuristic’s simulation budget (1,000; 3,000; 10,000 replications) affects the overall costs of MRP, RPS, and ConWIP. We focus on the relaxed CRL setting because, as shown in Section 5.3, it exhibits the strongest performance contrasts: MRP is competitive only

at low utilization, whereas ConWIP dominates in all other cases. Since the tight CRL scenario shows nearly identical budget-related patterns, the relaxed CRL results provide the most informative view of simulation-budget-driven refinement. Because the results for MRP, RPS, and ConWIP follow highly similar patterns across all experiments only the MRP results (Figure 9) are described in the main text. Detailed performance metrics and the corresponding parameter configurations for RPS and ConWIP are provided in Figure 10 and Figure 11 Appendix B.

The results for MRP (Figure 9) show that increasing the simulation budget consistently lowers overall costs across all settings, though this comes at the price of proportionally rising replication runtimes. A comparable performance pattern is observed for RPS (Figure 10); however, reflecting its simpler control logic, RPS average runtimes remain noticeably faster than those of MRP and are also notably faster than ConWIP (Figure 11).

Higher simulation budgets yield small but consistent cost reductions across all shop structures, with stronger improvements at higher utilization. Only the Flow Shop at 0.93 utilization shows negligible differences. As expected, average replication runtimes increase with the budget due to the larger set of historical values processed by the algorithm, a well-known characteristic of simulation optimization methods where higher accuracy is obtained at the expense of increased computational effort (Tekin and Sabuncuoglu 2004).

Across all PPCS, the results confirm the stability and robustness of the simheuristic: higher simulation budgets reliably improve solution quality while keeping runtime behavior stable (Chen et al. 2000; Fu 2002). These findings answer RQ3, demonstrating that larger budgets enhance solution refinement without compromising runtime feasibility.

Figure 9: Overall costs for MRP and Relaxed CRL across simulation budgets

5.5 Simheuristic-Derived Planning Parameters for Items and Components

This subsection describes the planning-parameter configurations identified by the simheuristic for each PPCS under tight and relaxed due-date settings. In contrast to the pre-simulation study – where all items and components shared a single parameter value per PPCS – the simheuristic now evaluates item-specific and component-specific parameter settings. The resulting configurations, summarized in Table 8a (tight) and Table 8b (relaxed) can be found in Appendix C. The tables present average values aggregated across all items or components associated with each parameter.

For MRP across all shop structures, the comparison between tight and relaxed due-date settings shows a systematic adjustment of the planning parameters. With relaxed due dates, the simheuristic generally selects higher planned lead times, while FOP lot sizes and safety-stock proportions tend to decrease, and these effects become more pronounced at higher utilization.

For RPS, the simheuristic yields the same reorder points and FOQ lot sizes for all items and components, unchanged across tight and relaxed due dates. This follows from RPS logic: it does not use item- or

component-specific future demand information, so the candidate parameters are uniform for all entities (Hopp and Spearman 2011).

Across tight and relaxed due-date settings for ConWIP, a similar pattern emerges: with increasing utilization, at least one of the key parameters – FOQ or WIP-Cap – tends to rise to absorb congestion. Such congestion-driven adjustments are consistent with ConWIP’s design as a WIP-regulated system (Spearman et al. 1990; Jodlbauer and Huber 2008; Hopp and Spearman 2011). This is particularly visible in Flow and Hybrid Shops, with one exception in the Hybrid Shop under tight due dates at 0.90 utilization.

For all PPCSs, the simheuristic generates more granular and context-sensitive parameter settings than the pre-simulation study, capturing item- and component-level variability. MRP and ConWIP show systematic adjustments to utilization, shop structure, and due-date tightness, while RPS remains largely uniform. Overall, the resulting configurations better accommodate congestion and structural complexity, aligning with broader evidence that fine-grained parameter tuning improves adaptability in complex production systems (April et al. 2003; Juan et al. 2015; Chica et al. 2020).

6 CONCLUSION

This research deepens the understanding of how the PPCS – Material Requirements Planning (MRP), Reorder Point Systems (RPS), and Constant Work-in-Progress (ConWIP) – perform in realistic, stochastic multi-stage production system structures (Flow-, Job- and Hybrid Shop). It further demonstrates how simulation-based optimization using a simheuristic can systematically refine their planning parameters across relaxed and tight customer-required lead-time settings and three utilization levels (85%, 90%, 93%), from which three main conclusions emerge.

First, our study reveals clear performance regimes: MRP is the most efficient choice for systems with low utilization (80%) and relaxed due dates. However, a critical transition occurs as system pressure increases. Once planned utilization reaches 85%, and especially at the 93% threshold, the applied multi-loop ConWIP shows its structural superiority. By decoupling WIP-caps at the item level, ConWIP reduced overall costs by up to 59.9% (see e.g., Flow Shop results) compared to the baseline without simheuristic. This demonstrates that the decoupling of parameters is not merely a design expansion, but a theoretical necessity to unlock the performance of pull-based systems in congested, complex environments.

Although the results indicate that the RPS is constrained by its reactive logic — as it triggers orders only when inventory falls below a reorder point and thus lacks predictive demand planning — it offers distinct advantages in specific contexts. In complex, multi-stage production systems with deep BOM structures, a very large number of items, and limited computational time, RPS represents a computationally efficient and planning-stable alternative to MRP and ConWIP. However, its inability to dynamically adjust to stochastic item-level fluctuations renders it insufficient for high-load, multi-stage systems where WIP synchronization is required to maintain throughput.

Second, the simheuristic effectively exploits item- and component-level parameterization, yielding substantial cost reductions beyond the baseline configurations identified in the pre-simulation study. These improvements persist even at high utilization levels, indicating that targeted parameter tuning can mitigate congestion effects without altering the underlying system logic.

Third, increasing the simulation budget systematically improves solution quality across all PPCS while only marginally affecting replication runtime. This confirms the robustness of the simheuristic and provides practical guidance: simulation budgets can be selected according to available computational resources and required precision without risking unstable or misleading parameter recommendations.

Future research may incorporate additional uncertainty sources, such as machine failures or demand seasonality. Alternative PPCS including DBR and DDMRP could be explored, as well as other system structures such as convergent BoMs. Additionally, future work could investigate data-driven parameter initialization and adaptive simulation budget allocation.

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DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that support the findings of this study are available in Zenodo at 10.5281/zenodo.18022077 upon reasonable request to Wolfgang Seiringer.

DISCLOSURE STATEMENT

The authors declare no competing interests.

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DECLARATION OF GENERATIVE AI AND AI-ASSISTED TECHNOLOGIES IN THE MANUSCRIPT PREPARATION PROCESS.

During the preparation of this manuscript, the authors used ChatGPT 5.2 (OpenAI) and Gemini 3 (Google) to improve language clarity and readability. All content was reviewed and edited by the authors, who take full responsibility for the final manuscript.

APPENDIX A (PSEUDOCODES)

Table 7: Variables and their meanings across all four algorithm modules: Main simheuristic Flow, SBM, SA, and ERR.

Variable	Meaning
Main SimHeuristic Flow	
<i>warmupIter</i>	Number of initial iterations during which neither SBM, SA nor ERR is active.
<i>minReps</i>	Minimum number of replications required to start SBM.
<i>maxReps</i>	Maximum number of replications performed per iteration.
<i>simulationBudget</i>	Total number of replications allowed.
<i>consumedBudget</i>	Cumulative number of replications executed.
<i>iteration</i>	Structure storing iteration-related auxiliary information.
<i>iteration.IterCount</i>	Global iteration counter.
<i>iteration.ReplCount</i>	Number of replications executed in the current iteration.
<i>currentSolution</i>	Parameter vector currently evaluated via simulation.
<i>baseSolution</i>	Reference solution used by the SA acceptance logic.
<i>bestSolution</i>	Best solution identified across all completed iterations.
<i>lb[p]</i>	Lower bound of parameter p in the sampling distribution.
<i>ub[p]</i>	Upper bound of parameter p in the sampling distribution.
<i>mode[p]</i>	Mode of the triangular sampling distribution for parameter p .
<i>minGap</i>	Minimum admissible width of the parameter interval.
<i>skipIteration</i>	Indicator returned by SBM for early termination of a replication.
<i>reduceRangeSBM</i>	Flag signaling that ERR should be applied.
<i>endWarmup</i>	Logical flag indicating whether the warmup phase has ended.
<i>bestPreSimulationSolution</i>	Solution from the pre-simulation study used for initialization.
SBM Module	
<i>SBMub</i>	Upper percentile bound guiding the SBM acceptance threshold.
<i>SBMlb</i>	Lower percentile bound guiding the SBM acceptance threshold.
<i>SBMArray</i>	Sorted vector of historical iteration averages for percentile extraction.
<i>percentilStep</i>	Percentile decrement applied per replication within an iteration.
<i>percentil</i>	Current percentile applied for the early-stopping criterion.
<i>pValue</i>	Percentile value derived from <i>SBMArray</i> and stopping threshold.
<i>avgCost</i>	Mean value over completed replications of the current iteration.
<i>globalCostLimit</i>	Absolute global cost upper bound.
SA Module	
<i>baseValue</i>	Value associated with <i>baseSolution</i> .
<i>bestValue</i>	Value associated with <i>bestSolution</i> .
<i>currentSolution.cost</i>	Value of the currently evaluated solution.
Δ	Improvement measure
<i>credit</i>	Tolerance for accepting slightly worse solutions.
<i>SAreset</i>	Countdown controlling daemon resets of the SA reference solution.
<i>defaultSAreset</i>	Reset value to which <i>SAreset</i> is re-initialized.
<i>accepted</i>	Indicator returning whether <i>currentSolution</i> is accepted by SA.
<i>newBest</i>	Indicator signifying that <i>currentSolution</i> becomes new global best.
ERR Module	
α	Shrink factor determining the contraction of parameter bounds.
<i>mid</i>	Solution value of parameter p used as new interval center.
<i>radius</i>	Half-width of the contracted parameter interval after shrinkage.
<i>(newLb, newUb)</i>	Updated bounds for parameter p following the shrink step.

Algorithm 1 SimHeuristic Overview

Initialization

- 1: Set *warmupIter*, *minReps*, *maxReps*
- 2: Set *simulationBudget*, *SBMub*, *SBMlb*, *lb[p]*
- 3: Set *ub[p]*, *mode[p]*, *minGap*
- 4: *SAReset* \leftarrow *defaultSAReset*
- 5: *credit* \leftarrow 0, *endWarmup* \leftarrow *false*
- 6: *consumedBudget* \leftarrow 0, *iteration* \leftarrow 0
- 7: Update parameter ranges (*lb[p]*, *ub[p]*) and modes *mode[p]* based on *bestPreSimulationSolution*
- 8: *baseSolution* \leftarrow *bestPreSimulationSolution*

Main Loop

- 9: **while** *consumedBudget* < *simulationBudget* **do**
- 10: *currentSolution* \leftarrow TRIANGULARSAMPLE(*lb[p]*, *ub[p]*, *mode[p]*)
- 11: *iteration.IterCount* ++
- 12: *skipIteration* \leftarrow *false*
- 13: *reduceRangeSBM* \leftarrow *false*
- 14: **while** *iteration.ReplCount* < *maxReps* \wedge *skipIteration* = *false* **do**
- 15: *Simulate*(*currentSolution*)
- 16: *iteration.ReplCount* ++
- 17: *consumedBudget* ++
- 18: **if** *iteration.IterCount* > *warmupIter* \wedge *iteration.ReplCount* > *minReps* **then**
- 19: *skipIteration* \leftarrow SBM()
- 20: **end if**
- 21: **end while**
- 22: **if** *iteration.ReplCount* = *maxReps* **then**
- 23: *reduceRangeSBM* \leftarrow *true*
- 24: **end if**
- 25: *iteration.ReplCount* \leftarrow 0
- 26: *newBest* \leftarrow *false*
- 27: **if** *iteration.IterCount* > *warmupIter* **then**
- 28: (*accepted*, *newBest*) \leftarrow SA(*currentSolution*)
- 29: **else**
- 30: *accepted* \leftarrow *true*
- 31: **end if**
- 32: **if** *iteration.IterCount* > *warmupIter* \wedge (*newBest* \vee *reduceRangeSBM*) **then**
- 33: ERR(*bestSolution*)
- 34: **end if**
- 35: **if** *accepted* \wedge *iteration.IterCount* > *warmupIter* **then**
- 36: *baseSolution* \leftarrow *currentSolution*
- 37: **end if**
- 38: Update parameter ranges (*lb[p]*, *ub[p]*) and modes *mode[p]* based on *baseSolution*
- 39: **end while**

Algorithm 2 SBM Module

```

1: function SBM
  Initialization
2:   Set  $minReps$ ,  $maxReps$ ,  $SBMub$ ,  $SBMlb$ 
3:    $skipIteration \leftarrow false$ 
  SBM percentile check
4:   Compute previous iteration averages  $A$  (non-zero)
5:    $SBMArray \leftarrow$  sort ascending
6:    $percentilStep \leftarrow (SBMub - SBMlb)/(maxReps - 1)$ 
7:    $percentil \leftarrow SBMub - (percentilStep * (iteration.ReplCount - 1))$ 
8:    $pValue \leftarrow$  percentile of  $SBMArray$  at  $percentil$ 
9:    $avgCost \leftarrow$  current mean cost of  $currentSolution$ 
10:  if  $avgCost > globalCostLimit \vee avgCost > pValue$  then
11:     $skipIteration \leftarrow true$ 
12:  end if
13:  return  $skipIteration$ 
14: end function

```

Algorithm 4 ERR Module

```

1: function ERR( $bestSolution$ )
2:   for all  $p$  do
3:      $mid \leftarrow bestSolution[p]$ 
4:      $radius \leftarrow (1 - \alpha)(ub[p] - lb[p])/2$ 
5:      $(newLb, newUb) \leftarrow (mid - radius, mid + radius)$ 
6:     if  $newUb - newLb < minGap$  then
7:        $(newLb, newUb) \leftarrow (mid - minGap/2, mid + minGap/2)$ 
8:     end if
9:     Update bounds of  $p$  to  $(newLb, newUb)$ 
10:  end for
11: end function

```

Algorithm 3 SA Module

```

1: function SA(currentSolution)
2:    $\Delta \leftarrow \text{baseValue} - \text{currentSolution.cost}$ 
3:    $\text{baseValue} = \text{baseSolution.cost}$ 
4:    $\text{accepted} \leftarrow \text{false}$ 
5:    $\text{newBest} \leftarrow \text{false}$ 
6:   if  $\text{baseValue} \geq \text{bestValue}$  then
7:      $\text{SAreset} \leftarrow \text{SAreset} - 1$ 
8:   end if
9:   if  $\text{SAreset} = 0$  then
10:     $\text{baseSolution} \leftarrow \text{bestSolution}$ 
11:     $\text{baseValue} \leftarrow \text{bestValue}$ 
12:     $\text{SAreset} \leftarrow \text{defaultSAreset}$ 
13:  end if
14:  if  $\Delta > 0$  then
15:     $\text{accepted} \leftarrow \text{true}$ 
16:     $\text{credit} \leftarrow \Delta$ 
17:     $\text{baseSolution} \leftarrow \text{currentSolution}$ 
18:     $\text{baseValue} \leftarrow \text{currentSolution.cost}$ 
19:    if  $\text{currentSolution.cost} < \text{bestValue}$  then
20:       $\text{bestSolution} \leftarrow \text{currentSolution}$ 
21:       $\text{bestValue} \leftarrow \text{currentSolution.cost}$ 
22:       $\text{newBest} \leftarrow \text{true}$ 
23:       $\text{SAreset} \leftarrow \text{defaultSAreset}$ 
24:    end if
25:  else if  $-\Delta \leq \text{credit}$  then
26:     $\text{accepted} \leftarrow \text{true}$ 
27:     $\text{credit} \leftarrow 0$ 
28:     $\text{baseSolution} \leftarrow \text{currentSolution}$ 
29:     $\text{baseValue} \leftarrow \text{currentSolution.cost}$ 
30:  else if  $\text{currentSolution.cost} < \text{baseValue}$  then
31:     $\text{accepted} \leftarrow \text{true}$ 
32:     $\text{baseSolution} \leftarrow \text{currentSolution}$ 
33:     $\text{baseValue} \leftarrow \text{currentSolution.cost}$ 
34:  else
35:     $\text{accepted} \leftarrow \text{false}$ 
36:  end if
37:  return ( $\text{accepted}, \text{newBest}$ )
38: end function

```

APPENDIX B (IMPACT OF SIMULATION BUDGET)

The RPS results (Figure 10) show a comparable pattern: increasing the simulation budget consistently lowers overall costs in all settings, while replication runtimes rise proportionally. Nonetheless, RPS average runtime remains noticeably faster than MRP, reflecting its simpler control logic.

Figure 10: Overall costs for RPS and Relaxed CRL across simulation budgets

For ConWIP (Figure 11), higher simulation budgets again lead to consistent cost reductions across all utilization levels. ConWIP shows the longest replication runtimes, exceeding both MRP and RPS, mainly due to the two ConWIP loops for items and components and the upstream MPS lotsizing logic, which increase computational load.

Figure 11: Overall costs for ConWIP and Relaxed CRL across simulation budgets

Appendix C (SIMHEURISTIC-DERIVED PLANNING PARAMETERS)

The results in Table 8a and Table 8b highlight a key advantage of the simheuristic approach: it enables the identification of item- and component-specific parameter values, rather than relying on a single uniform setting as in the pre-simulation study. This finer granularity allows the method to respond to differences in variability and congestion across material levels, as documented in the inventory-control and production-planning literature (Silver et al. 1998; Enns and Suwanruji 2004; Axsäter 2015).

For MRP the concrete adjustments illustrate this: in the Flow Shop at 0.93 utilization, planned lead times increase by +1.2 for items and +1.1 for components, while FOP drops by -1.3 for components but only +0.5 for items. Similar patterns occur in the Hybrid Shop, where component planned lead times rise by +1.6, compared to +0.8 for items. This pattern reflects the fact that components enter production earlier and are, therefore, more directly affected by cumulative waiting times, making their optimal parameter levels more sensitive to changes in timing and congestion. This aligns with established findings that lower-level components experience amplified variability and congestion effects due to cumulative waiting times (Spearman and Zazanis 1992; Hopp and Spearman 2011).

With a dynamic iteration-based seed and identical candidate sets across due-date settings, the sampling pattern — and thus the selected parameters — remains the same and leads to identical parameter values for RPS across shop type and lead time setting. Still, Table 8a and Table 8b show a meaningful structure: both reorder points and FOQ sizes rise with utilization, and item-level values are consistently higher than component-level ones where components exist. This reflects congestion-driven adjustments in the evaluated parameter space, even though RPS itself cannot exploit additional BOM- or demand-specific information. This behavior is consistent with findings that reorder-point systems remain structurally insensitive because they do not incorporate BOM or lead-time variation (Axsäter and Rosling 1993; Stevenson et al. 2005).

For ConWIP, the simheuristic identifies differentiated FOQ and WIP-cap values at item and component level (where components exist), while estimated lead times and work-ahead buffers remain identical for both. This separation of item- and component-level parameters contributes to the cost improvements over the pre-simulation study

Table 8a: Minimum Overall Costs and Parameterization of Pre-Simulation Study (Tight Setting).

Env.	Due date tightness Production system structure Planned shop load	Tight [0 days fix + E[10] days variable CRL]								
		Flow Shop			Job Shop			Hybrid Shop		
		0.85	0.90	0.93	0.85	0.90	0.93	0.85	0.90	0.93
MRP	Planned lead time items [days]	1.90	2.80	3.00	4.20	5.20	6.00	2.80	3.70	3.50
	FOP lot size items [days]	1.50	2.80	2.70	1.50	2.80	3.30	1.80	2.60	2.50
	Safety stock items [prop. demand]	1.70	1.40	1.30	0.20	1.90	1.60	0.80	1.00	1.40
	Planned lead time components[days]	1.50	3.00	3.00	-	-	-	2.70	3.70	2.70
	FOP lot size components [days]	2.00	2.70	3.30	-	-	-	2.00	3.30	3.30
RPS	Safety stock components [prop. demand]	1.70	0.70	1.50	-	-	-	0.50	1.30	2.00
	Reorder-point items [prop. demand]	4.90	5.10	5.70	8.40	9.00	9.60	5.90	5.90	6.70
	FOQ lot size items [prop. demand]	1.40	1.50	1.50	1.60	3.10	3.60	1.40	1.40	1.40
	Reorder-point components [prop. demand]	5.20	5.20	6.00	-	-	-	6.00	5.80	6.70
ConWIP	FOQ lot size components [prop. demand]	0.70	0.70	0.80	-	-	-	0.80	0.80	0.90
	MPS FOQ lot size items [prop. demand]	1.40	1.80	2.00	1.00	2.50	3.30	1.80	1.70	1.80
	MPS FOQ lot size components [prop. demand]	1.70	1.50	2.00	-	-	-	1.20	2.00	2.50
	WIP-Cap item / items [workload in Tsd. minutes]	62,025	63,246	61,569	63,628	59,342	118,978	59,745	59,229	60,066
	WIP-Cap item / components [workload in Tsd. minutes]	61,280	60,358	61,401	-	-	-	62,713	58,972	50,175
	Estimated lead time components & items [days]	3.60	3.50	3.50	6.30	5.30	7.80	3.50	3.40	4.10
	Work-ahead-window buffer [days]	0.00	0.30	0.70	0.20	0.50	0.50	0.00	0.70	0.50

Table 8b: Minimum Overall Costs and Parameterization of Pre-Simulation Study (Tight Setting).

Env.	Due date tightness Production system structure Planned shop load	Relaxed [10 days fix + E[10] days variable CRL]								
		Flow Shop			Job Shop			Hybrid Shop		
		0.85	0.90	0.93	0.85	0.90	0.93	0.85	0.90	0.93
MRP	Planned lead time items [days]	2.80	2.60	4.20	4.20	5.00	6.60	3.00	2.90	4.30
	FOP lot size items [days]	1.60	1.80	3.20	1.70	2.50	3.40	1.50	1.70	2.60
	Safety stock items [prop. demand]	0.30	0.90	0.30	0.20	1.70	2.00	0.30	1.80	0.50
MRP	Planned lead time components [days]	2.70	3.30	4.10	-	-	-	2.30	2.30	4.30
	FOP lot size components [days]	1.30	2.00	2.00	-	-	-	1.30	2.00	2.00
	Safety stock components [prop. demand]	0.00	0.70	0.70	-	-	-	0.30	1.70	0.40
RPS	Reorder-point items [prop. demand]	4.90	5.10	5.70	8.40	9.00	9.60	5.90	5.90	6.70
	FOQ lot size items [prop. demand]	1.40	1.50	1.50	1.60	3.10	3.60	1.40	1.40	1.40
	Reorder-point components [prop. demand]	5.20	5.20	6.00	-	-	-	6.00	5.80	6.70
RPS	FOQ lot size components [prop. demand]	0.70	0.70	0.80	-	-	-	0.80	0.80	0.90
	MPS FOQ lot size items [prop. demand]	1.40	1.70	1.70	1.10	3.10	3.40	1.50	1.50	1.40
	MPS FOQ lot size components [prop. demand]	1.00	1.50	2.50	-	-	-	1.00	1.70	1.70
ConWIP	WIP-Cap item / items [workload in Tsd. minutes]	59,581	57,715	60,613	61,277	56,088	118,323	61,850	62,311	59,417
	WIP-Cap item / components [workload in Tsd. minutes]	58,501	64,554	55,964	-	-	-	57,967	58,187	56,587
	Estimated lead time components & items [days]	3.60	3.50	5.30	6.10	6.10	9.10	3.40	3.50	5.40
ConWIP	Work-ahead-window buffer [days]	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.30	0.60	0.60	0.00	0.00	0.00